

Redefining Marital Fulfillment: A Phenomenological Study of Childless Couples

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Abstract

In pronatalist societies like the Philippines, involuntary childlessness is often stigmatized, challenging the identity of married couples. This study explores the lived experiences of five (5) couples who have remained childless for over five years, utilizing a qualitative phenomenological design grounded in Stigma Management Communication Theory (SMCT). Data gathered through in-depth, semi-structured interviews revealed that couples navigate their reality through specific identity negotiation strategies. The analysis identified four key themes: (1) the externalization of cause, where couples attribute infertility to medical realities and "God's will" to buffer self-esteem; (2) an emotional dichotomy characterized by a tension between "ambiguous loss" and dyadic contentment; (3) the role of the extended family as a critical protective buffer against community stigma; and (4) adaptive coping through social parenthood. The study concludes that the Filipino value of "*bahala na*" functions as active spiritual surrender rather than passive fatalism, serving as a potent tool for stigma management. Recommendations focus on marriage and family counseling, specifically the integration of narrative reframing and spiritual interventions to foster resilience and validate non-biological parenting roles.

Keywords: Involuntary Childlessness, Childless Couple, Marital Fulfillment, Stigma Management Communication Theory, Social Parenthood, Marriage and Family Counseling

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1. Introduction

Marriage has long been associated with the expectation of having children, with parenthood frequently framed as a defining marker of marital fulfillment, family continuity, and social identity (McQuillan et al., 2025). Across many cultural contexts, particularly in collectivist societies, the absence of children can lead to questions about marital success and personal completeness, often resulting in stigmatization or social exclusion (Dhar, 2013; Tabong & Adongo, 2013). Yet, an increasing number of couples experience marriage without becoming parents, whether by deliberate choice or due to circumstances such as infertility (Blackstone & Stewart, 2012; Mascarenhas et al., 2012). This evolving social reality calls for a re-evaluation of the traditional narrative that equates marital satisfaction solely with childbearing (Hansen, 2012; Twenge et al., 2003).

Existing literature reveals that childlessness is a multi-dimensional experience shaped by personal, relational, and sociocultural factors. Scholars argue that the conventional voluntary-involuntary distinction does not sufficiently capture the complexity of childless experiences. Añis et al. (2024) demonstrate that for some individuals, the path to childlessness is an active choice influenced by personal history, while for others, it arises from external disruptions, resulting in a complex spectrum of emotions. These decisions are often compounded by systemic factors; Ahmadzadeh Tori et al. (2023) reveal that voluntary childlessness is frequently driven by a combination of individual preferences and social aspects, including financial constraints and forced circumstances, suggesting that government welfare and educational support play a crucial role in family planning decisions. Sociocultural expectations also play a prominent role in these dynamics. Adhikary et al. (2024) emphasize that cultural norms, stigma, and community pressures significantly influence how childless couples perceive themselves and negotiate their identity within society.

Infertility-related studies further highlight the emotional and social challenges faced by couples, especially women. In developing countries, infertility can cause substantial psychological distress and diminished social standing, underscoring the need for healthcare providers to understand the cultural context in which infertility occurs (Dyer, 2002). This is supported by van Balen and Bos (2009), who identify childlessness as a major life problem with significant psychological consequences, particularly in low-resource areas where the social and cultural repercussions are profound yet understudied. At the relational level, Kailaheimo-Lönnqvist et al. (2024) show that life satisfaction among childless individuals can influence both their own and their partner's levels of depression, underscoring the importance of mutual emotional support and shared coping mechanisms.

Despite the challenges, much of the literature also documents positive marital outcomes among childless couples. LaMastro (2001) reports that many couples experience happiness, security, confidence, and optimism in their marital relationship, challenging the stereotype of the unhappy childless union. However, the psychosocial state of these couples is fragile; Dhar (2013) notes that childless couples' experiences are deeply influenced by social culture, which directly affects their coping strategies. The process of navigating a

childless marriage is shaped by how these strategies are employed, whether constructive or ineffective (Mohammadi et al., 2018). From a life-course perspective, Rybińska and Morgan (2019) identify distinct pathways toward childlessness, including the postponement of childbearing and prolonged indecision. Additionally, Ngai and Loke (2022) underscore the significance of family cohesion, adaptability, and social support in reducing infertility-related stress, particularly among couples navigating societal pressures.

Although these studies collectively enrich our understanding of childlessness, several gaps remain. Much of the literature focuses on either the psychological consequences of infertility or the sociocultural pressures associated with not having children. Less attention has been given to the holistic lived experiences of married couples who remain childless, how they construct meaning within their marriage, negotiate external expectations, and cultivate satisfaction despite societal assumptions about parenthood. Furthermore, limited research explores the interplay of emotional, relational, and cultural factors that shape the marital journey of such couples.

Therefore, this study aims to explore the experiences of childless couples in marriage, examining the evolution of their relationships, the challenges they encounter, and the sources of fulfillment they cultivate. By moving beyond the traditional assumption that marital success is tied to parenthood, this research seeks to provide a deeper and more inclusive understanding of how childless couples navigate their lives together. The study contributes to the broader field by addressing gaps in the literature, offering insights into the diversity of marital experiences, and challenging persistent societal narratives surrounding marriage and childbearing.

2. Methodology

This study employed a qualitative phenomenological research design to deeply explore the lived experiences of childless couples within a society dominated by a pronatalist narrative. Grounded in the theoretical underpinnings of Stigma Management Communication Theory (Meisenbach, 2010), this approach was selected to capture how stigma is discursively constructed and managed through the dynamic interactions of married life. By utilizing a qualitative lens, the research aimed to deconstruct the complex psychological, emotional, and social pressures faced by couples who deviate from the traditional reproductive norm, providing a richness of data that quantitative methods could not achieve.

The research was conducted across diverse geographical settings in the Philippines to capture a broad spectrum of experiences. Data collection took place in the municipalities of Kapatagan and Sultan Naga Dimaporo in the province of Lanao del Norte, as well as in the municipality of Aurora in Zamboanga del Sur. To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon, the researchers utilized purposive sampling to select five (5) married couples who have remained childless for a minimum of five years. This specific duration was chosen because, in the Philippine context, societal inquiries and pressures regarding reproduction typically intensify significantly after the first few years of marriage (De Los Angeles, 1965; Tudy & Tudy, 2020). The selected participants exhibited a range of marital

durations, including couples married for five, seven, nine, eleven, and fifteen years, thereby providing a longitudinal perspective on how couples navigate the evolving stigma and challenges of a child-centric culture over time.

The primary instrument for data collection was the researcher, who utilized a self-designed, semi-structured interview guide to elicit personal narratives. To ensure the instrument's validity and sensitivity to the delicate nature of the topic, the guide was subjected to review by three external validators prior to deployment. The data gathering process spanned a total of two months, from March to May 2024. Informants were identified through a "call for informants" utilizing referrals from co-workers and relatives. All data were gathered through face-to-face in-depth interviews, a method chosen to facilitate genuine interaction and allow for the observation of non-verbal cues often associated with sensitive topics like infertility and social exclusion.

Data analysis was conducted using a rigorous thematic approach, following the framework established by Braun and Clarke (2006), to interpret the narratives through the lens of the study's theoretical foundation. Following the verbatim transcription of audio recordings, the researchers systematically identified recurring words, phrases, and statements. These were categorized to reveal patterns of expression and stigma management, specifically analyzing how couples embody their family identity despite the absence of children, a dynamic explored in the Philippine context by Cabonce et al. (2019). This analytical process allowed the researchers to identify how couples construct meaning and resilience in the face of external societal expectations.

In qualitative inquiry, the researcher is considered the primary instrument of analysis; thus, acknowledging positionality is essential to ensuring the trustworthiness of the study (Berger, 2015). As a member of the Filipino society in which this study is situated, the researchers possessed an inherent familiarity with the local cultural nuances, specifically the pervasive pronatalist narratives that equate family completeness with childbearing. This cultural insider status facilitated the establishment of rapport and allowed for a deeper sensitivity to the non-verbal cues and indirect communication styles often used by participants when discussing sensitive topics like stigma and infertility. However, to mitigate the risk of projecting personal biases or societal assumptions onto the participants' narratives, the researcher practiced reflexivity throughout the research process (Berger, 2015). This involved the phenomenological technique of epoché or bracketing, wherein the researcher deliberately set aside personal beliefs, experiences, and judgments (Berger, 2015) regarding parenthood and marriage to remain open to the participants' unique lived realities. By maintaining a reflexive journal, the researcher continuously monitored how their own background and interactions might influence the data, ensuring that the findings remained grounded strictly in the voices of the childless couples rather than the researcher's preconceptions.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the research process to protect the dignity and rights of the participants. The researchers ensured informed consent by providing a detailed letter explaining the study's purpose and obtaining formal, voluntary permission from all participants. Participation was strictly voluntary, with no coercion or

monetary compensation, and participants were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. To protect the privacy of the couples, strict confidentiality and anonymity were maintained; no real names or identifying details were disclosed in the final report, ensuring that the participants were shielded from further potential stigmatization or gossip within their respective communities.

3. Results and Discussion

This section elucidates the phenomenological experiences of involuntarily childless couples in the Philippines. Through the lens of Stigma Management Communication Theory (Meisenbach, 2010), we analyze how these couples construct their identity, navigate the pronatalist expectations of Filipino society, and employ specific coping mechanisms to maintain marital stability.

The analysis yielded four major themes: (1) The Externalization of Cause: Medical Realities and Divine Will; (2) The Emotional Dichotomy: Oscillating Between Optimism and Distress; (3) The Buffer System: Family Dynamics and Social Support; and (4) Adaptive Coping: Spiritual Surrender and Social Parenthood.

3.1. The Externalization of Cause: Medical Realities and Divine Will

The participants unanimously identified their childlessness as involuntary, stemming from a convergence of biological constraints and spiritual timing. This dual attribution serves as a primary stigma management strategy, allowing couples to externalize the blame away from their personal agency or moral failing.

3.1.1. Medical Factors and Biological Infertility

Participants openly acknowledged physiological barriers, including male factor infertility (impotence) and female reproductive health issues.

"Akong bana impotent sya, maoy dili maka-anak." (My husband is impotent, that is why we can't have a baby.) [Respondent 1] *"Akong asawa naay bikil sa matris niya mao di mi ka anak."* (My wife is infertile, that is why we can't have a baby.) [Respondent 2]

The acknowledgment of medical factors aligns with global literature suggesting that the medicalization of infertility can sometimes reduce stigma by framing the issue as a biological malfunction rather than a character flaw (Greil et al., 2011). However, in developing contexts, the psychological burden remains heavy. Vashkar et al. (2017) note that without adequate psychosocial intervention, these biological realities often cascade into depression and social dysfunction.

3.1.2. Theology of Waiting: "God's Time"

A distinct cultural nuance observed in this study is the heavy reliance on what initially appears to be religious fatalism but is more accurately identified as active spiritual coping. Participants viewed their situation not merely as a medical failure, but as a spiritual waiting period.

"*Wala pa jud mi tagae sa Ginoo...magtagad rami kanus-a mi tagaan.*" (We haven't been blessed by God yet...we will just wait for when we are given.) [Respondent 3]

This narrative reflects the deep-seated Filipino value of "*bahala na*" (Menguito & Teng-Calleja, 2010). While early interpretations framed this attitude as passive resignation, modern psychological frameworks in the Philippine context define it as "determination in the face of uncertainty" and an active "search for the sacred" (Menguito & Teng-Calleja, 2010). Rather than surrendering hope, the couples are surrendering control, effectively engaging in what Lagman et al. (2014) describe as "leaving it to God." By externalizing the timing of parenthood as "God's will" rather than internalizing it as a personal physiological failure, couples construct a protective buffer for their self-esteem. This culturally specific coping mechanism aligns with global findings by Romeiro et al. (2017), who argue that religious coping is a critical moderator of infertility stress, particularly in highly religious Catholic societies like the Philippines.

3.2. The Emotional Dichotomy: Oscillating Between Optimism and Distress

The lived experience of the couples is not monolithic. It is characterized by a complex tension between marital satisfaction and existential distress.

3.2.1. Marital Optimism and Dyadic Cohesion

Contrary to the stereotype that childless marriages are inherently unhappy, several couples reported high levels of contentment, focusing on financial freedom and companionship.

"*Okay ra man, kontento pa pud mi nga kami pa duha, maglaag lang mi...and gatigum.*" (We're okay with just the two of us, we're content spending time together...and saving money.) [Respondent 3]

This validates the "response shift" phenomenon (Chao et al., 2014; Ortega-Gómez et al., 2022; Vanier et al., 2021) observed in quality-of-life studies, where individuals adapt their internal standards to match their reality. As noted by Zapanta et al. (2023), focusing on the dyadic relationship rather than the missing triad (child) allows couples to cultivate resilience. Furthermore, recent Western studies suggest that childless couples often report higher relationship quality than parents due to increased time for emotional intimacy (Hansen, 2012; Keizer & Ivanova, 2017).

3.2.2. The Burden of the "Empty Nest"

However, this optimism is frequently punctuated by distinct emotional distress, manifesting as feelings of inadequacy, anxiety, and envy.

"*Malipayon, pero maibog mi sa mga pamilya nga adunay mga anak.*" (We're happy, but we envy families with children.) [Respondent 2] "*Pressured, usahay mawal-an mig pag-asa, iblame amo self...*" (Feeling pressured, sometimes we lose hope, blaming ourselves...) [Respondent 1]

This supports the concept of "ambiguous loss" (Boss, 2002), where the couple grieves a child that is psychologically present, in their hopes, but physically absent (Okoro Rellias, 2015). Cocchiaro et al. (2020) and Espinol (2021) emphasize that this cycle of hope and disappointment is a primary driver of anxiety in infertile couples.

3.3. The Buffer System: Family Dynamics and Social Support

In a collectivist society, the extended family plays a pivotal role (Li et al., 2025). The study reveals that the family acts as a double-edged sword: a source of pronatalist pressure, but also the primary source of stigma buffering.

3.3.1. Moral Support vs. Societal Pressure

While societal pressure is pervasive, the immediate families of the respondents largely provided "protective buffering."

"Ila mi ingnan na mag-ampo lang perminte and di mi nila ipressure jud..." (They tell us to just pray and not to pressure ourselves...) [Respondent 5]

This finding nuances the existing literature. While Adhikary et al. (2024) highlight community stigma, this study suggests that the immediate family often circles the wagons to protect the couple. Al Sabbah et al. (2025) and Mohaddesi et al. (2022) corroborate that high family support significantly mitigates the negative psychological impacts of infertility. The family reinforces the "God's time" narrative, validating the couple's status despite the lack of children.

3.4. Adaptive Coping: Spiritual Surrender and Social Parenthood

The couples employed active coping strategies to navigate their reality. Two dominant strategies emerged: religious coping and social parenthood.

3.4.1. Religious Coping

Prayer and church attendance were not passive activities but active strategies to manage anxiety.

"Isalig ang kaguol sa Ginoo..." (We entrust our sorrow to God...) [Respondent 1]

Nwaomah & Dube (2018) posit that religion provides a cognitive framework that makes suffering meaningful. By surrendering control to the divine, the couples alleviate the burden of fixing their medical condition, which reduces the psychological strain of self-blame.

3.4.2. Adoption and Social Parenthood

Perhaps the most profound finding is the redefinition of parenthood. When biological conception failed, couples turned to adoption or focused on nieces and nephews.

"Nag-adopt mi ug bata dayun mao amo gipa-eskwela..." (We adopted a child and then we sent them to school...) [Respondent 3]

This illustrates the concept of "social parenthood." In the Philippines, the practice of *pag-ampon* (informal adoption) allows childless couples to perform parental roles without biological ties. This aligns with Daly (1987) and Tracz (2022), who argue that adoption facilitates a transition from infertile couple to family, effectively neutralizing the social stigma of childlessness. By investing resources in nieces, nephews, or adopted children, these couples fulfill the generative need to nurture the next generation (Erikson, 1963), thereby reclaiming their social identity as productive adults.

4. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1. Summary of Findings

This study elucidates the phenomenological experiences of involuntarily childless couples in the Philippines, analyzing their identity construction through the lens of Stigma Management Communication Theory (Meisenbach, 2010). The findings reveal that couples navigate the pronatalist expectations of Filipino society not through passive resignation, but by employing specific, active coping mechanisms that foster marital stability.

The participants unanimously attribute their childlessness to a convergence of medical realities and divine will, a dual attribution that serves as a primary stigma management strategy. By framing their situation as "God's time," couples utilize the Filipino cultural value of "*bahala na*" as a form of active spiritual surrender rather than fatalism. This externalization of cause allows them to shift the blame away from personal inadequacy, effectively buffering their self-esteem against the psychological impact of biological infertility.

Emotionally, the marital experience is characterized by a complex dichotomy between optimism and distress. While couples grapple with the ambiguous loss of a hoped-for child and feelings of envy, they simultaneously demonstrate a response shift by recalibrating their expectations. Many couples report high levels of contentment derived from financial freedom and deepened dyadic companionship, challenging the stereotype that childless unions are inherently unhappy.

Socially, the study highlights the pivotal role of the extended family, which functions as a protective buffer. Although societal pressure remains pervasive, immediate family members often reinforce the couple's spiritual narrative, validating their status and mitigating the sting of community stigma. Finally, couples achieve adaptive coping by redefining parenthood itself; through religious devotion and the practice of social parenthood, such as adoption or investing in nieces and nephews, they fulfill their generative needs and successfully transition their identity from infertile to socially productive adults.

4.2. Conclusion

This study challenges the pervasive deficit narrative often associated with involuntary childlessness in pronatalist cultures. By examining the lived experiences of Filipino couples through the lens of Stigma Management Communication Theory (SMCT), the implications of these findings are fundamentally reframed: childlessness is revealed not merely as a private medical condition or a state of lack, but as a complex social performance of identity negotiation. SMCT illuminates that the couples' behaviors are not passive reactions to

tragedy, but strategic communicative acts designed to manage their social standing. Through this theoretical lens, the reliance on "*bahala na*" and the attribution of fertility to God's will are understood not as fatalistic resignation, but as discursive tools used to externalize blame. By linguistically shifting the locus of control to the divine, couples successfully decouple their biological status from their moral worth, thereby accepting the factual reality of childlessness while rejecting the stigmatizing label of failure or incapability.

Furthermore, the application of SMCT underscores that resilience in this context is relational and communicative rather than purely intrapsychic. The theory highlights how social parenthood serves as a stigma reduction strategy that allows couples to perform the socially required role of nurturer without the biological requisite. This suggests that the psychological well-being of childless couples is heavily dependent on their ability to successfully communicate a valid family identity to their community. Consequently, a fulfilling marriage in this context is defined by the couple's shared capacity to construct and maintain a resilient narrative that withstands external pronatalist pressure.

4.3. Recommendations for Marriage and Family Counseling

Based on the findings regarding stigma management and marital resilience, the following clinical implications are proposed specifically for marriage and family counselors:

4.3.1. Adoption of Narrative Reframing Techniques

Counselors may utilize narrative therapy techniques aligned with Stigma Management Communication Theory to help couples reconstruct their identity. Therapists may guide couples in shifting their internal narrative from one of biological failure to one of spiritual waiting or chosen resilience, thereby helping them regain a sense of agency and shared purpose.

4.3.2. Integration of Spiritually-Oriented Interventions

Given the prevalence of "*bahala na*" as an active coping mechanism, practitioners may incorporate spiritual assessments into the counseling process. Rather than viewing religious fatalism as a barrier to agency, counselors may validate the theology of waiting for God's time as a legitimate psychological buffer that protects the couple's self-esteem and reduces anxiety.

4.3.3. Enhancement of Dyadic Cohesion

Therapy sessions may prioritize the strengthening of the marital subsystem independent of the parental role. Counselors may encourage couples to invest in shared non-reproductive goals such as financial stability, travel, or mutual hobbies to cultivate the response shift observed in the study, where satisfaction is derived from companionship rather than child-rearing.

4.3.4. Navigation of Extended Family Boundaries

Recognizing that the extended family serves as both a buffer and a source of pressure, counselors may assist couples in establishing healthy communication boundaries. Interventions may focus on equipping couples with assertive communication scripts to manage pronatalist inquiries from relatives while identifying specific family members who can serve as supportive allies.

4.3.5. Facilitation of Social Parenthood Roles

To address the psychological need for generativity, therapists may introduce social parenthood as a therapeutic goal. Counselors may help couples explore and validate alternative nurturing roles such as adoption, fostering, or active avuncular involvement as fulfilling pathways to achieving a complete family identity.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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